

COLORING SUBSTANCES HARMALS

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В статье представлены результаты спектрофотометрического исследования водно-спиртовых экстрактов из семян гармалы и водного извлечения из всего растения, проведенного с целью подтверждения наличия красящих веществ - алкалоидов в указанных экстрактах.

Ключевые слова: гармала, красящие вещества, алкалоиды, гармалин.

The article presents the results of a spectrophotometric study of water-alcohol extracts from harmala seeds and water extraction from the whole plant, carried out in order to confirm the presence of dyes - alkaloids in these extracts.

Key words: harmala, coloring matter, alkaloids, harmaline

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The chemical composition of harmala includes a large number of compounds, such as organic acids, steroids, fatty oil, proteins, carotenoids, saponins. The seeds contain up to 14.2% fatty oil and dyes. Flowers, leaves and stems are rich in potassium, iron, magnesium, zinc, strontium in high concentrations. Microelements include copper, manganese, chromium, nickel, aluminum, lead [1, 2]. But the most remarkable compounds in harmala are alkaloids, the content of which is most significant in seeds: harmine (banisterol), harmalol, harmaline (harmidine), harman, vazicinon, peganin (vazicin), deoxypeganin, deoxyvazicinone, peganidin, pegamin, peganol, dipegin, hinaldin and others. It is the alkaloids that harmala owes its numerous therapeutic effects: antiseptic, anticholinesterase, antispastic, hypnotic, antiemetic and anthelmintic. The coloring matter of harmala is harmaline [3], the content of which is up to 95% of the total amount of alkaloids [2]. Harmaline - 4,9-dihydro-7-methoxy-1-methyl-3H-pyrido [3,4-b] indole - refers to alkaloids, derivatives of indole and has the following structural group, which is characterized by the presence of a quaternary nitrogen atom, which causes the main properties of this compound:

Therefore, harmaline, like another natural dye, the alkaloid berberine, belongs to the technological type of basic dyes [4].

To confirm the presence of alkaloids in the aqueous-alcoholic extract of harmala seeds and the aqueous extract from the whole plant, we took UV spectra of these extracts. Figure 1 shows the UV spectrum of an aqueous-alcoholic extract of harmala seeds.

Fig. 1. UV spectrum of aqueous-alcoholic extract of harmala seeds

The method of obtaining extracts, the spectra of which are shown in Fig. 1 are somewhat different: option 1 - the extract was obtained without potassium nitrate, option 2 - the extract was obtained without ammonium chloride, option 3 - the extract was obtained without adding potassium nitrate and ammonium chloride, option 4 - the extract was obtained according to a well-known technique. As can be seen from the figure presented, the UV spectra of the aqueous-alcoholic extract of harmala seeds obtained by various methods are practically the same. They contain a broad, intense absorption band at 380 nm and an absorption band at 200 nm. In the UV spectrum of this compound, there is an absorption maximum at a wavelength of 241 nm and 301 nm, typical for an indole ring conjugated with an aromatic heterocycle. The data correspond to those described in the literature.

Literature:

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